

STIFFNESS REDUCTION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES DUE TO DELAMINATION*

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, based on Pipes-Pagano problem, quasi-3D element method is employed to study the stiffness-reduction in composite laminates due to through delaminations between the composite layers. From the analysis, the development of damage can be divided into three stages. In the first stage, a sharp decrease in stiffness occurs followed by a linear decrease (second stage), and during the third stage, a sharp drop in stiffness precedes fracture.

INTRODUCTION

A commonly observed failure mode in laminated composite materials is delamination between the composite layers. Delamination may develop during manufacture due to incomplete curing or the introduction of a foreign particle; they may result from impact damage; or they may result from interlaminar stresses that develop at stress-free edges or discontinuities. Furthermore, delamination may grow under cyclic loading.

Delamination growth redistributes the stresses in the plies of a laminate, and may influence residual stiffness, residual strength, and fatigue life. Hence, a fatigue analysis for composite materials should take into account the presence and growth of delamination.

A summary of experimental and analytical work on delamination were done by Rybicki, Schmueser and Fox¹. One of the most promising techniques for characterizing delamination growth is based on the rate of strain energy released, G .

O'Brien² presented a method for analyzing the onset and growth of delaminations in composite materials. The linear stiffness relationship was used to derive a closed-form equation for the strain energy release rate, G , associated with delamination growth in unnotched laminates.

In this paper, based on Pipes-Pagano problem³, quasi-3D element method⁴ is employed to study the stiffness-reduction in composite laminates due to symmetric through delaminations between the composite layers. From the calculations, the development of damage can be described as three stages.

FUNDAMENTAL EQUATIONS AND MECHANICAL MODEL

Rather than a plane stress state, a three-dimensional stress state is considered in the elasticity approach of Pipes and Pagano³ to the problem of delamination. The stress-strain relations for each orthotropic

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layer in laminate coordinates as shown in Fig.1 are⁵,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{11} & \bar{C}_{12} & \bar{C}_{13} & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{16} \\ \bar{C}_{12} & \bar{C}_{22} & \bar{C}_{23} & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{26} \\ \bar{C}_{13} & \bar{C}_{23} & \bar{C}_{33} & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{36} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{44} & \bar{C}_{45} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{45} & \bar{C}_{55} & 0 \\ \bar{C}_{16} & \bar{C}_{26} & \bar{C}_{36} & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_z \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{zx} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1 Pipes-Pagano problem

The strain-displacement relations are,

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= U, x & \epsilon_y &= V, y & \epsilon_z &= W, z \\ \gamma_{yz} &= V, z + W, y & \gamma_{zx} &= W, x + U, z & \gamma_{xy} &= U, y + V, x \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

If the laminate is subjected to uniform axial extension ϵ_0 on ends $x = \text{constant}$, then all the stresses are independent of x . The stress-displacement relations are obtained by substituting the strain-displacement relations, Eq(2), in the stress-strain relations, Eq(1). Next, the stress-displacement relations can be integrated under the condition that all stresses are functions of y and z only. After imposing symmetry and antisymmetry conditions, the displacements are,

$$\begin{aligned} u &= kx + U(y, z) \\ v &= V(y, z) \\ z &= W(y, z) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where k is a constant.

The stress equilibrium equations then reduce to,

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xy,y} + \tau_{zx,z} &= 0, & \sigma_{y,y} + \tau_{yz,z} &= 0, \\ \tau_{yz,y} + \sigma_{z,z} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Upon substitution of the displacement field, Eq (3), in the stress-displacement relations and subsequently in the stress equilibrium differential equations, Eq (4), the three displacement equilibrium equations are, for each layer, functions of $U(y,z)$, $V(y,z)$ and $W(y,z)$. They can be written in matrix form:

$$\{U\} = [N] \{q\} \quad (5)$$

where $[N]$ is the shape functions, $\{q\}$ is the displacements of nodes of the element. Here, the method of isoparametric element with eight nodes is employed. Then, the geometrical relations can be expressed as,

$$\{\epsilon\} = \{\epsilon_0\} + [B] \{q\} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\{\epsilon\}^T = \{\epsilon_x \quad \epsilon_y \quad \epsilon_z \quad \gamma_{yz} \quad \gamma_{zx} \quad \gamma_{xy}\} \quad (7)$$

$$\{\epsilon_0\}^T = \{\epsilon_0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0\} \quad (8)$$

and $[B]$ is strain matrix.

By the principle of the least strain energy, the stiffness matrix and nodal forces of the element are,

$$[k] = \iint_{A_m} [\bar{B}]^T [\bar{C}] [\bar{B}] dA \quad (9)$$

$$\{f\} = \iint_{A_m} [\bar{B}]^T [\bar{C}] \{\epsilon_0\} dA \quad (10)$$

Then the equilibrium equations of the system will be

$$[K] \{q\} = F \quad (11)$$

where $[K]$ and $\{F\}$ are the stiffness of the system and nodal forces of the system respectively.

The through delaminations are considered as shown in Fig. 1(b). Due to symmetry, one quarter section is considered. The corresponding elements and constrained supports are shown in Fig.2. The residual stiffness of the damaged laminates is,

$$E = \sigma_m / \epsilon_m \quad (12)$$

where σ_m and ϵ_m are the average nodal stress and strain along x-axis. The reduction of stiffness is,

$$D = \frac{E_0 - E}{E_0} = 1 - \frac{E}{E_0} \quad (13)$$

where E_0 is the Young's modulus of the undamaged composite, D is called damaged parameter.

Fig.2 Elements and constrained supports

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

For a high modulus graphite/epoxy composite material with,

$$E_1 = 138.2 \text{ GPa} \quad E_2 = E_3 = 14.5 \text{ GPa}$$

$$G_{12}=G_{23}=G_{31}=5.88 \text{ GPa} \quad \nu_{12}=\nu_{23}=\nu_{31}=0.21$$

in a laminate with $2b=0.4064 \text{ m}$ (width) and $h=0.0254 \text{ m}$ (thickness of each layer). The laminate is $(45/-45)_s$ as shown in Fig.3.

For verification, the distribution of interlaminar stresses $\sigma_x, \tau_{xy}, \tau_{xz}$ is shown in Fig.3. Obviously, they agree well with the results by Elasticity Solution⁶.

Fig.3 Comparison between quasi 3D finite element method and Elasticity Solution

Fig.4 The interlaminar stress τ_{xz} distribution for different delamination lengths

The interlaminar stress τ_{xz} distributions with different lengths of delamination is shown in Fig.4. Obviously, the length of delamination has a major effect on the interlaminar stress distribution. The residual stiffness E versus the length of delamination is shown in Fig.5. From this curve, the development of damage can be divided into three stages. In the first stage, a sharp decrease in stiffness occurs followed by a linear decrease (stage II), and during the third stage, a sharp drop in stiffness precedes fracture. The major part of this curve is linear stiffness relationship which is agreeable to O'Brien's presentation².

The damage parameter D versus the length of delamination is shown in Fig.6. This curve is composed of three stages too.

Fig.5 Residual stiffness vs. delamination length for $(45/-45)_s$ laminate

Fig.6 Damage parameter vs. delamination length for (45/-45)_s laminate

For cross-ply (0/90)_s laminates, the residual stiffness is independent of the length of delamination, as shown in Fig.7. This result is agreeable to that there are only transverse cracks with no delamination in cross-ply laminates.⁸

Fig.7 Residual stiffness vs. delamination length for (0/90)_s laminate

CONCLUSION

1. For the delamination of off-axis ply laminates, the development of damage can be divided into three stages. In the first stage, a sharp decrease in stiffness occurs followed by a linear decrease (stage II), and during the third stage, a sharp drop in stiffness precedes fracture.

The major part (stage II) is linear stiffness relationship which is agreeable to O'Brien method².

2. For cross-ply laminates, the residual stiffness is independent of the length of delamination. This result is agreeable to the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) micrograph of the edge section.

3. 3D finite element method will be employed to analyze the stiffness reduction in composite laminates due to random distribution of delamination.

REFERENCES

1. Rybicki, E.F., D.W. Schmuesser and J.Fox, J. Composite Materials, 11(1977), 470.
2. O'Brien, T.K., Characterization of Delamination Onset and Growth in a

- Composite Laminate, Damage in Composite Materials, ASTM STP-775 (1982), 140.
3. Pipes, R.B. and N.J. Pagano, Interlaminar Stresses in Composite Laminates Under Uniform Axial Extension, J.Composite Materials, 4(1970), 538.
 4. Ye, L. and B.X. Yang, Nonlinear Finite Element Analysis of Interlaminar Stresses in Composite Laminates, ACTA MATERIAE COMPOSITAE SINICA, 4(2)(1987), 44.
 5. Jones, R.M., Mechanics of Composite Materials, McGraw Book Co.,(1975), 213.
 6. Wang, S.S. and I. Choi, J. Applied Mechanics, 49(1982), 541.
 7. Whitcomb, J.D., I.S. Raju and J.G. Goree, Computer & Structures, 15(1982), 23.
 8. Highsmith, A.L. and K.L. Reifsnider, Stiffness Reduction Mechanisms in Composite Laminates, Damage in Composite Materials, ASTM STP-775 (1982), 103.